

The role of psychological defense mechanisms in personal development

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Annotation. This scientific article contains theories of scientists about the psychological mechanisms of personality, factors motivating the use of individual defense mechanisms, and the reasons for their occurrence.

Keywords. Person, psychological defense mechanisms, mental model, I, Id, Super ego.

Introduction By its nature, the human race was created as such a complex creature that for millennia they have been considered the object of study by many sciences. Studying a person biologically and physiologically requires studying the internal and external structure of the body in which he exists, and psychologically, studying his psyche, which is invisible to the human eye and untouchable.

Main part It is well known that in the period before Freud, psychology was a science that studied the conscious states of person. A scientist, on the other hand, departed from the notion that psychology is a science that studies only conscious states, and proved that it is a science that studies unconscious states of a person, and laid the foundations of psychoanalysis.

Between 1890 and 1897 the scientist put forward his first ideas on psychopathology. The scientist also studied in detail the psychological factors of hysterical states and introduces the concept of protecting neurosis, which is the "core of the psychic mechanism", and calls it compressive [2]. Later this concept began to be understood as one of the defense mechanisms.

The concept of a defense mechanism is one of the most comprehensive concepts. This is one of the main phenomena of many sciences. However, in psychology this term is regarded as a power that makes the psyche easier. This concept is widely used in psychology today, and a lot of research is currently being carried out.

The term “defense” is the earliest expression of a dynamic position in psychoanalytic theory. The term “defense” was first discovered in Freud’s book called “Protective neuropsychosis” in 1894. Later, this term began to appear in many other works concerning “I” as a force against the negative information, events and negative experiences that occur in the human psyche [3].

Freud defined his fundamental basis for psychological defense mechanisms in the treatment of patients with neurosis and noted that this is a reversible disease that occurs under the influence of negative psychological states.

Patients with neurosis mainly complain about emotional disorders, disorders of the body and autonomic functions. The basis of these diseases are events that arise as a result of a conflict of personal relations with conflicting life situations. A person who cannot resolve such a conflict creates internal discomfort and tension within himself. According to Z. Freud, in such a difficult situation for a person, it is activated by special mechanisms of psychological protection in order to protect the human mind from unpleasant and negative influences. The functioning of protective mechanisms in an individual is accompanied by the creation of a feeling of subjective relief and relief from stress.

Throughout a person’s life, he or she will witness many misfortunes and unsuccessful events. It's no secret that they negatively affect the psyche. At this time, psychological defense mechanisms act as a means of temporary assistance to him and soothe his psyche.

In this regard, Freud's daughter A. Freud made some changes to the concept of her father. A. Freud emphasizes the importance of defense mechanisms in solving social problems. Protection mechanisms consider a person as a product of developing and studying *I*. It also promotes the idea that the set of protective mechanisms is individual and characterizes the level of human adaptability to society.

Later it became clear that the protective mechanisms began to be considered not only as an element of the psyche of people with a neurosis, but also as a function of the *I*, which is a conscious part of any human psyche. Since then, many scientists have been engaged in scientific research to study the mechanisms of psychological protection of the individual psyche [1].

A. Freud, like his father, also identifies several types of defense mechanisms and gives their chronological classification. Each protective mechanism is primarily intended

for the assimilation of certain instinctive impulses, and therefore it has been shown that it is associated with a certain stage of development of the child.

Among the protective mechanisms, squeeze out or Compressive extrusion is the main mechanism, and it takes precedence over all means of protection *I*. This raises a problematic question. It remains unclear when and how a certain mechanism of *I* will be applied. An attempt has been made to explain this problem by approaching defensive processes, such as compression, projection, introjection, regression.

Compression is mainly used to fight against the sexual needs. They suggest that the person is dealing with unwanted thoughts that come back to him again if the defense mechanism cannot squeeze out other defense methods. Since each protective mechanism is primarily intended for the assimilation of certain instinctive impulses, they are associated with a certain stage of development of the child.

A person can use the mechanisms of psychological protection only after the exchange of information in three models of the psyche - *I*, *Id* and *Super I*. For example, compression is the removal or elimination of emotions and thoughts from the *I*. This mechanism cannot be applied by a person in childhood. Its use requires a certain age. The mechanisms of projection and introjection, in contrast to squeezing/compression, try to distinguish the *I* from the outside world. If there is no difference between the external environment and *I*, a person cannot use these mechanisms. Sublimation, on the other hand, means replacing an instinctive goal with a higher social value and accepting, or at least knowing that value, which in turn implies the existence of a *Super-Ego*. This protective mechanism can also be applied by a person to others who are at a later stage of development, depending on the point of view of the period of use of the projection and introjection. Only when a person learns to let go of what he does not need for *I* in the external environment can he soften it.

This means that all protective mechanisms can be applied by a person in a certain situation and development. As mentioned above, a person uses protective mechanisms to remove various psychological effects from the mind that lead to depression, fear and affective states, and so on. But how do they appear?

The protective conditions that we are all familiar with in analysis are the tools that form the basis of neurosis in older people. The protective process is the assimilation and satisfaction of certain instinctive desires in the mind through the *I*. At first, the *I* does not resist this, but the *Super I* resists. The peculiarity of this process is that the *I* does not consider the impulse that he observes to be dangerous. This is because the

reasons for the protection will not concern him in the first place. Instinct is the enemy. The reason for this is that the *Super I* forbids satisfaction, and if it achieves its goal, it will undoubtedly cause difficulties in the relationship between the *I* and the *Super I*. Therefore, a person is afraid of instinctual desires, because he is concerned about the severance of his relationship with the *I* and *Super I*.

If a person's attention is focused on protecting himself from instincts, then the *Super I* is a terrible force for him. *Super I* is a conspirator who does not allow *I* to form friendships with instincts. *Super I* seeks to create the perfect pattern in a person. This prohibits the satisfaction of sexual needs in a person. Thus, the *I* is completely deprived of its independence, obeys the *Super I* and cannot enjoy it.

From the above considerations, it is clear that the *I* of a person by nature is not a self-sufficient subject. The *I* becomes a zone of anti-instinct, as it moves from the principle of pleasure to the principle of reality. The *I* looks at the intense power between the *Super I* and *Id* on its territory. However, if the *I* believes that the higher forces are gone from *Id* or the demands of instinctual impulses are exaggerated, his hostility to instincts turns into a state of anxiety.

At the heart of protecting the *I* from instincts is protection from affect. When the *I* seeks to protect itself from instinctive motives based on stated motives, it rejects influences associated with instinctive processes. The nature of these affects is insignificant: they can be pleasant, painful, or dangerous for the *I*. If affect is associated with a prohibited instinctive process, its fate is decided in advance. In the condition of connection, it will be enough to warn the *I* against him.

In addition, the basis of protection against affect lies simply in the conflict between the *I* and instinct. Satisfying instinct is always a pleasant thing. However, affect can be pleasant or unpleasant in nature. If the *I* has no influence on the instinctive process and at the same time does not reject the influence, its relation to the instinctive process is completely determined by the principle of pleasure. Because he loves pleasant feelings and protects himself from unpleasant things. *I* is ready to reject affect if affect is associated with forbidden sexual impulses, and they are unpleasant [2].

Conclusion

It is assumed that situations in the above cases cause a person to experience depression, fear, affective and other negative emotional states.

In some cases, the prohibitions imposed by *Super I* are allowed through protective mechanisms, but they create the possibility of re-awareness without completely

disappearing from consciousness. In the situations that have arisen, information that has been deleted, forgotten and rejected by the mind, when it returns the mind in unconscious way, it puts a person in a very difficult situation.

If a person has depression, fear, affect and other conditions as a result of the requirements of the *Super I*, then those who raise a child should avoid everything that leads to the formation of very demanding *Super I*. They should provide easier training methods developed by them. They should provide easier training methods developed by them. They should be tolerant of them, and not be too strict in the identification process. And finally, a person's aggression must be transmitted to the outside world so that it is not harmful and does not penetrate inside. If the upbringing is successful, people will get rid of the worries and neuroses that arise in life, will be able to enjoy and will not suffer from internal conflicts.

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